

Integrating a Converis CRIS/RIMS with DMPRoadmap and Export/Import maDMP from Figshare

Niklas Zimmer, Norman Smith, Ya'qub Ebrahim, Peter Neish (University of Melbourne), Joakim Philipson (Stockholm University), Brian Riley (DMPRoadmap - California Digital Library). Lyle Winton (University of Melbourne)

<https://gist.github.com/peterneish/92b59a90f5e05096c3709669f459c749>

The general goal was to integrate DMP Roadmap and Figshare as much as possible with the requirements of the RDA DMP Common Standard. We wanted this to be a complete round-trip integration to enable interoperability in both directions. In some cases there will already exist a DMP in Figshare, but in other cases, we wanted to see if this could be created from the existing Figshare metadata, or imported from a DMP system such as DMP Roadmap. An example workflow is shown below.

Uploading a DMP to Figshare

A prototype was developed that converts an RDA Common Standard DMP into the JSON format expected by the Figshare system. The converted JSON is then sent to the Figshare API,

where a Figshare project is created as a placeholder and a DMP item is created with the referenced DMP ID, title and description. This will be useful for DMP tool developers because it provides an example of how they can allow their users to publish/submit their DMPs into a repository.

Prototype code from *Lyle Winton*: [upload maDMP to Figshare](#).

Extract a DMP from Figshare

A prototype was written to allow a user to enter in a search term and then retrieve a DMP in the RDA Common Standard format. The code searches the Figshare API using the user's search term and then displays a list of results. The user can then click on a link that converts the Figshare JSON record into the Common Standard format. This may become useful once Figshare has a larger collection of DMPs stored in their repository.

Prototype code from *Brian Riley*: [Figshare_to_maDMP](#).

Outcomes

The team was able to successfully import and export DMP metadata from the Figshare system. The prototypes generated are particularly useful because they illustrate the ability and approach to take when using the RDA Common Standard to integrate with repository systems.

A further idea was discussed about updating the [DMPRoadmap code](#) to allow developers to write plugins for various repositories like Figshare and Zenodo. Plugin development could then be contributed back to the DMPRoadmap community to allow the various installations of the codebase to quickly enable integration with repositories.